

Comparison studies on morphology and optical properties of thin film CdS by chemical bath deposition and spin coating technique

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Abstract

The thin film of cadmium sulfide (CdS) was deposited on a soda lime glass substrate by chemical bath deposition (CBD) and spin coating technique. In CBD technique, the deposition was performed at 60°C, 70°C, 80°C and 90°C during various deposition times (30, 60, 90 and 120 min). In spin coating technique, CdS film was deposited at 1600 rpm, 1800 rpm, 2000 rpm, 2200 rpm and speeds of 2500 rpm. The morphological, chemical composition and optical properties of CdS film were investigated for both techniques using the scanning electron microscope (SEM), energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) and the UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer. From these investigations, an appropriate CdS film was obtained which is related to uniform deposition, the equal contribution of the atomic percentage Cd and S, band gap value ~ 2.42 eV, high transmittance and low resistivity. Such optimized CdS film will perform as an n-type window layer for thin film solar cell.

Keywords: CdS, chemical bath deposition, spin coating, morphological properties.